

**STUDY OF THE MATERIAL COMPOSITION OF COPPER-
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Abstract: Chemical analysis of average ore samples revealed the following average contents of valuable components: Cu – 0,51%; Mo – 0,006%; Au – 0,34 c/s; Ag – 2,85 c/s. Copper content in free oxidized minerals is 2.37%, associated with oxidized minerals – 0.39%, in secondary sulfides – 2,76%, and in primary sulfides – 94,48%. Based on these data, it can be concluded that the studied ore samples belong to the sulfide type of porphyry copper deposits. Mineralogical studies revealed the following main types of mineralized rocks with metasomatic alterations: andesitic porphyrite, andesidacite, rhyolite, rhyolite breccia, sericite-feldspar-quartz metasomatites, granite, granite porphyry, leucocratic granite, gneissic rocks, and quartzite-like rocks.

Keywords: copper, molybdenum, gold, silver, element, mineral, valuable component, ore, sulfide, spectral, chemical, optical emission spectral analysis, granulometric composition.

Introduction: Currently, there are a large number of deposits containing rare metals such as gold, silver, copper and molybdenum. Each type of such raw materials, depending on the characteristics of its composition and the state of gold and rare metals in it, requires a specific approach to the extraction of these rare metals. The processing of minerals is conditionally divided into three large groups according to the geological

form of occurrence of rare metals, material composition, particle size, location of deposits and methods of gold extraction: enrichment, hydrometallurgical (chemical effects) and pyrometallurgical (thermal effects). A lot of research is being carried out on the mining industry and enrichment and processing of minerals in our republic [1;2]. This article presents the results of studying ore samples and the material composition of their primary mechanical enrichment products. The formation of ores is explained geologically as follows. There are three main types of endogenous mineralization of real geological and industrial gold deposits: gold-quartz, gold-sulfide-quartz, twelve subtypes of gold-sulfide. The gold-sulfide-quartz geological and industrial type includes deposits that contain sulfides (pyrite, chalcopyrite, galena, sphalerite), lead, copper, silver sulfate salts, tellurides of gold, silver, bismuth and other ore minerals. from 6 to 25% (most often - from 10 to 15% by weight). Gold in the ores is both free (in quartz) and associated with sulfides, tellurides and sulfate salts [3;4]. The insufficient extraction of valuable components is explained by the imperfection of technologies for extracting gold, silver and copper from ore raw materials, such as gravity, amalgamation, percolation. Due to the depletion of gold, copper, molybdenum, and silver ore deposits and the use of valuable components and raw materials with complex composition in the processing process, modern and highly efficient technologies for their extraction are necessary [5;6]. The development of the mining industry has led to the formation of large-scale extraction and processing [7;8].

Research methods: this research work used modern complex research methods, including laboratory experiments and methods of processing the results of experiments using chemical, mineralogical, optical-emission, spectral and analytical analyses.

Research results: The material composition of the miscon samples was studied using spectral, chemical, analytical, rational, optical emission spectral, mineralogical and other types of analyses. The processes of selecting, testing, processing and preparing samples in the research, as well as the design and interpretation of the experiments performed are one of the important aspects on which the results of the

subsequent research depend. The preparation of the technological sample was carried out by manual sampling in accordance with the requirements of GOST 14180-80, which consists of the following stages: sampling, averaging it using the “ring and cone” method and quartering [9;10]. The granulometric composition of the studied material was determined by sieving. For the study, a sample weighing at least 5 kg, dried in an oven until the mass stabilized, was distributed over a set of standard sieves in accordance with GOST 2851-75. The sieved products were weighed on a scale in accordance with GOST 29329-92. The content of copper, molybdenum, gold and silver in each size class was determined and the distribution of components by size class was calculated.

Granulometric characteristics of the ore sample. To determine the distribution of the main valuable components by size class, the initial ore samples crushed to the size class -3+0 mm were sieved. The results of the sieve analysis are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Results of the sieve analysis of the ore sample

Classes, mm	Exit, %	Quantity				Distribution, %			
		c/s		%		Au	Ag	Cu	Mo
		Au	Ag	Cu	Mo				
-3,0+2,5	5,67	0,25	2,41	0,433	0,003	4,12	4,80	4,52	2,52
-2,5+1,4	7,38	0,27	2,50	0,45	0,004	5,79	6,48	6,11	4,37
-1,4+1,0	18,82	0,30	2,58	0,458	0,004	16,39	17,06	15,86	11,16
-1,0+0,5	22,76	0,31	2,60	0,465	0,005	20,49	20,79	19,47	16,87
-0,5+0,315	9,91	0,32	2,63	0,47	0,005	9,21	9,16	8,57	7,34
-0,315+0,25	4,65	0,32	2,67	0,472	0,006	4,32	4,36	4,04	4,13
-0,25+0,18	3,79	0,35	2,75	0,484	0,007	3,85	3,66	3,37	3,93
-0,18+0,08	11,13	0,36	2,88	0,50	0,008	11,63	11,26	10,24	13,20
-0,08+0,044	4,0	0,42	3,30	0,72	0,011	4,88	4,64	5,30	6,52
-0,044+0	11,89	0,56	4,26	1,03	0,017	19,33	17,79	22,53	29,96
Ore	100	0,34	2,85	0,544	0,007	100	100	100	100

As can be seen from Table 1, the amount of valuable components in the studied ore samples, as a rule, increases in small size classes, which may be due to the uneven distribution of metals.

Grinding of ore samples. The grinding of the ore sample material was studied using a method developed by the MEKHANOB Institute (St. Petersburg, Russia).

Ore samples weighing 1 kg were ground in a 40 ml laboratory mill at different times. Grinding was carried out with a constant ball load in the ratio T: L: W=1: 0.75: 8. The ground product was passed through a 0.074 mm (200 mesh) sieve.

The dependence of the yield of the -0.074 mm class on the ore grinding time is shown in Figure 1.

Based on experimental data, the specific productivity of the laboratory mill was calculated by the following formula:

$$q = \frac{0.6 \cdot P \cdot (R_2 - R_1)}{V \cdot T} \quad t/m^3 \cdot \text{hour}$$

P - sample, 1 kg; V - mill volume, 7 dm³; T - grinding time, min;

R1 - class composition in the initial ore -0.074 mm, %; R2 - class composition in the crushed product -0.074 mm, %; The results of the experiments are presented in Tables 2 and 3. The curve of the relative productivity of the laboratory mill as a function of the time of grinding the ore is shown in Figure 1.

Table 2

Class productivity as a function of the time of grinding the ore -0.074+0mm

Mine name	-0.074mm class output %, grinding time min.						
	0	10	20	30	40	50	60
Miscon	14,7	46,69	68,17	78,81	85,2	88,89	90,24

Figure 1. -0.074 mm class output curve versus time

Table 3

Dependence of specific productivity of a laboratory mill on ore grinding time

Mine name	Mill production capacity, $t/m^3 \cdot \text{hour}$, Crushing time, min.					
	10	20	30	40	50	60
Miscon	0,300	0,229	0,183	0,151	0,127	0,108

As can be seen from Table 3, the highest productivity of the laboratory mill is observed in the grinding time range of 10-20 minutes.

Figure 2. Curve of specific productivity of the laboratory mill versus grinding time

Spectral analysis: The samples were subjected to diffraction spectrograph with a STE-1 dispersion intersected at the center of the AI VSMS GU IMR. The results of the spectral analysis are presented in table 4.

Table 4

Results of semi-quantitative spectral analysis
of average ore samples

Component	Amount, $n \cdot 10^{-3} \%$	Component	Amount, $n \cdot 10^{-3} \%$	Component	Amount, $n \cdot 10^{-3} \%$
Ba	<2,0	Cd	<0,1	Ni	<0,6
Be	<0,05	Co	7,0	Sn	0,7
V	10,0	Mn	50,0	Pb	100,0
Bi	<0,2	Cu	>1100	Ag	1,0
W	5,0	Mo	50,0	Sb	15,0
Ga	7,0	As	<2,0	Ti	200,0
Ge	0,5	Zn	30,0	Cr	2,0
Au	<0,03	Nb	<0,4	Ta	<10,0
Li	<3,0				

Chemical analysis. The results of a complete chemical analysis of the studied ore samples, carried out at the AI VSMS Center of the “IMR” IS, are presented in table 5.

Table 5

Results of a complete chemical analysis of average ore samples

Component	Amount, %	Component	Amount, %	Component	Amount, %
SiO ₂	65,5	S _{commo} n.	2,8	Na ₂ O	0,98
Fe ₂ O ₃ _{comm} on.	6,41	S _{sulfid} .	2,05	K ₂ O	0,8
Fe ₂ O ₃	4,26	SO ₃	1,88	CO ₂	1,75
FeO	1,94	P ₂ O ₅	0,39	MgO	1,5
TiO ₂	0,19	-H ₂ O	0,22	Au, c/s	0,34
MnO	0,05	Cu	0,51	Ag, c/s	2,85
Al ₂ O ₃	12,1	Mo	0,006	M.L.D.B.	6,16
CaO	3,75	As	undefined		

According to the results of chemical analysis of average ore samples, the average content of valuable components is: Cu-0,51%; Mo – 0,006%; Au-0,34 c/s; Ag-2,85 c/s. Assay analysis: The results of the assay analysis conducted in the analytical laboratory of the Central Laboratory are presented in Table 6.

Table 6

Results of analysis of average ore samples

Mine	Amount, c/s	
	Au	Ag
Miscon	0,4	<5

According to the analysis results, the amount of gold in the ore sample is 0.4 c/s gold and <5 c/s silver in the “Miscon” balanced ore; gold <0,2 c/s silver in the Miskan off-balance sample and <0,5 c/s silver.

Phase analysis. The occurrence of copper in the ore samples was studied. Use of phase analysis of the ore. Phase analysis of the ore for copper was carried out at the AIVSMS Center of the State Institution “IMR” according to the method M00193950.38-037:2017 “Methodology for measuring the mass fraction of copper compounds in ores by phase analysis” and their processing products by the atomic

absorption method, developed by the Central Analyst. Laboratory of "Almalyk KMK" JSC. The results of the phase analysis are presented in Table 7.

Table 7

Results of phase analysis of ore sample for copper

The shape of the copper	Mass fraction of copper, %	
	Absolute	Relative
Oxidized free minerals (cuprite)	0,012	2,37
Relationship with oxidized minerals	0,002	0,39
Secondary sulfides (chalcosine, covellite)	0,014	2,76
Primary sulfides (chalcopyrite)	0,479	94,48
All:	0,507	100

As can be seen from Table 7, the copper in the sample is represented by free oxidized minerals: 2,37%; 0,39% - bound to oxidized minerals; 2,76% - secondary sulfides and 94, 48% - primary sulfides. In general, we can conclude that the studied ore samples belong to the sulfide type of porphyry copper ores.

Mineralogical studies of selected technological samples from the mines of the Miskan deposit.

The mineral composition of the ores and ore production at the Miskan site was studied by a specialist from the State Institution "IMR". As a result of the work, the main types of ore mixing production, the chemical and mineral composition of ores and ore mixing production, the structural and textural properties of the ores, the composition and formation of the main and mineral components were determined.

As a result of the studies, the following main types of metasomatically altered, mineralized rocks were identified: andesitic porphyry, andesidacite; rhyolite, rhyolite breccia; sericite-feldspar-quartz metasomatite; granite; granite-porphyry; leucocratic granite; gneiss-like rock; quartz-like rock; quartz-feldspathic vein.

The chemical composition of the ores and ore-bearing rocks was determined by complete silicate analysis. Silicon dioxide (SiO_2) 65,5%, total alkalis ($\text{Na}_2\text{O}+\text{K}_2\text{O}$) 1.78%. CaO content 3,75%, MgO 1,5%. The total content of iron oxides reaches 6,41%. The content of sulfide sulfur in ores and mineralized ore rocks is 2,05%.

Quartz, plagioclase, sericite, chlorite, clay and carbonate minerals are found everywhere and are the main non-metallic minerals in the ore composition. Some samples contain potassium feldspar. Accessory minerals include zoisite, rutile, apatite and monazite.

Among the ore minerals in the ore sample, pyrite and chalcopyrite, magnetite, hematite, molybdenite, sphalerite, galena, covellite, chalcocite, bornite and others are found in small quantities or as single grains.

During the study, IMR employees identified about 32 minerals in the ores of the Miskan site (Table 9). Minerals are divided into the following groups: widespread, medium and rare. The main ore minerals include pyrite, chalcopyrite and magnetite. The group of medium minerals includes molybdenite, bornite, galena, sphalerite, rutile, etc. The group of less common minerals is represented by pyrrhotite, pyrargyrite, vittexenite, arsenopyrite, etc.

Among ore minerals, chalcopyrite and molybdenite are the main industrial minerals. In addition, bornite, covellite, chalcocite and vittexenite are often observed from copper minerals. Among the identified silver minerals, pyrargyrite and hessite (silver telluride) are also found.

It should be noted that pyrite is one of the most common minerals and contains highly bound components such as gold, silver, tellurium and selenium.

The texture of the ores is massive, veined, cellular, and diffuse. The structure is medium, coarse-grained, hypidiomorphic-grained, allotriomorphic-grained. Veins of pyrite, chalcopyrite-pyrite are developed along the fractures of the rock.

The main ore minerals were identified in the study of the composition of the gravilite. Pyrite and chalcopyrite dominate in the concentrates. The ratio of pyrite and

chalcopyrite content is mainly 3:1, 2:1, respectively. Magnetite and hematite are found in small quantities. Molybdenite, sphalerite, galena, arsenopyrite, bornite, covellite, chalcosine, pure silver, etc. are often observed.

Pyrite is mainly in the form of fragmented, xenomorphic, less often pentagonal-dodecahedral crystals. Most pyrite crystals are free; they are also observed in intergrowth with chalcopyrite, galena, and non-metallic minerals. Sometimes it contains inclusions of chalcopyrite and hematite.

Previous studies in pyrite have identified the following elements by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES) analysis. The following trace elements have been identified in pyrite: Au – 5,28-5,64 ppm; Ag – 2,02-2,39 ppm; Se – 2,29-3,04 ppm; Te – 0,487-0,527 ppm; Pb – 80,8-81,8 ppm; Zn – 57,3-78,8 ppm.

Chalcopyrite is a xenomorph with conchoidal fracture and blackening. It is found as free crystals and in close association with pyrite, galena, non-metallic minerals and hematite. It is sometimes noted as inclusions in pyrite. It develops along molybdenite fractures. According to ICP-mass spectrometric analysis, the following impurity elements have been identified in chalcopyrite: Au – 2,04 ppm; Ag – 20 ppm; Se – 56 ppm; Te – 2,5 ppm. Molybdenite occurs in the form of flattened, layered grains, prismatic crystals - single and rare grains.

It is observed in the form of free grains, as well as in association with chalcopyrite. Galena and sphalerite are rare. The shape of galena particles is cubic, angular xenomorphic. They are observed in the form of free grains intergrown with chalcopyrite and pyrite. Arsenopyrite is located in the form of free grains, surrounded by pyrite. The shape of the particles is rhombic, angular. Bornite is located in the form of free particles surrounded by chalcopyrite, located in single particles. The shape of the particles is xenomorphic, angular. Covellin develops along chalcopyrite. The shape of the particles is xenomorphic, elongated. Yozaret is located as free particles in artificial briquettes. The shape of the particles is angular. The size of the particles is 0,03x0,05 mm. Pure silver is located in single particles. It is noted in the form of thin

isometric inclusions in chalcopyrite. Magnetite and hematite are located in gravitational enrichment concentrates. They are closely related to each other. The mineral content in the concentrates ranges from 2-5% per grain. Pale ore. It is in the form of particles in artificial briquettes made from concentrates and polished pieces, the particle size is 0,01-0,05 mm. The shape of the particles is xenomorphic. Pale ore corresponds to tennantite in its optical properties.

Conclusion

According to the results of chemical analysis of average ore samples, the average content of valuable components is: Cu-0,51%; Mo – 0,006%; Au-0,34 c/s; Ag-2,85 c/s. The copper in the sample is 2,37% Cu when expressed in free oxidized minerals, 0,39% Cu bound to oxidized minerals, 2,76% Cu in secondary sulfides, and 94,48% Cu in primary sulfides. We can conclude that the studied ore samples belong to the sulfide type of porphyry copper ores. The texture of the ores is massive, cellular, veined, and disseminated. The structure is mainly medium and large-grained, hypidiomorphic, and allotriomorphic. Quartz, plagioclase, sericite, chlorite, clay, and carbonate minerals are found everywhere and are the main nonmetallic minerals in the ore composition. Some samples contain potassium feldspar. Accessory minerals include zoisite, rutile, apatite, and monazite. Pyrite and chalcopyrite predominate among ore minerals. Magnetite, hematite, molybdenite, sphalerite, galena, covellite, chalcocite, bornite, etc. Chalcopyrite and molybdenite are the main ore minerals of the industry. Ore minerals with microveined, micro-dispersed, filamentary, subgraphite, and replacement microstructures may be unfavorable for enrichment. The distribution of particles and the allotriomorphic grain structure of ore minerals also affect the opening of ore minerals and, accordingly, lead to the loss of useful components. The loss of chalcopyrite may be associated with its distribution in pyrite, magnetite, sphalerite and rock-forming minerals. The network microstructures characteristic of pyrite-chalcopyrite aggregates with numerous edge boundaries, voids, frames and microveins are also unfavorable. Under the microscope, chalcopyrite was observed to grow in a

similar way to molybdenite, sphalerite and galena, but their content was not so high. In graviboyite, the main part of chalcopyrite is in the form of free crystals. The mineral form of the main and associated components is in the form of their own minerals, as well as in the form of impurities in other ore minerals. The identified copper minerals are chalcopyrite, bornite, covellite and chalcocite; molybdenite is represented by molybdenite. The mineral form of lead is galena, zinc is sphalerite, bismuth, tellurium is vattexenite, yozerite. The minerals of gold have not been identified. It is included in the composition of sulfide minerals as impurities. The mineral form of silver is pyrargyrite, hessite and native silver. It is included in the composition of sulfide minerals as impurities. According to a scanning electron microscope, galena contains 2,55% silver. The silver content in chalcopyrite is 20 ppm, and in pyrite 10 ppm. Tellurium minerals include hessite and yozerite. It is also included in pyrite and chalcopyrite. The tellurium content in pyrite is 8,8 ppm, and in chalcopyrite 2,5 ppm. Analyzing these indicators, it can be said that it is possible to extract useful components at a high rate using gravity and flotation methods in the enrichment of Miskon ore samples.

REFERENCES

1. B. N. Khamidullaev, I. S. Nurmukhamedov, A. S. Usmonov, Sh. Yu. Samandarova. Study of the material composition of refractory gold ore. E.O. № 5. c. 14-18. (2024).
2. A.U. Samadov, B.N. Khamidullaev, I.M. Almatov, A.A. Normurodov. Results of enrichment of gold ore at the North-West Kyzylolmasay ore field site. E.O. № 4. p. 3-8. (2023).
3. I. V. Pestryak, V. V. Morozov, Ochir Erdenetuya, Erdenezul Zhargalsayhan. Experimental substantiation of requirements for the composition of circulating waters used in the processes of grinding and flotation of copper-molybdenum ore. E.O. № 1. p. 11-16. (2024).

4. G. E. Askarova, K. K. Mamyrbayeva, M. R. Shautenov, A. R. Mambetalieva. Intensification of gravity enrichment of refractory gold-bearing ores. E.O. №. 4. p. 18-24. (2024).
5. G.Zh. Abdykirova, B.K. Kenzhaliev, A.K. Koizhanova, D.R. Magomedov/Study of beneficiation of low-sulfide gold-quartz ore. E.O. №. 3, 15-18 (2020).
6. A.T. Abubakriev, A.K. Koizhanova, D.R. Magomedov, M.B. Erdenova, N.N. Abdyl daev/Leaching of gold-containing ores with application of oxidation activators . K.I.M.S. №. 3 (310). 10-15, (2019).
7. I.K. Umarova, S.T. Matkarimov, D.B. Makhmarezhabov/Development of technology for flotation enrichment of gold-bearing ores Amantaytau deposits. E.O. №. 2, pp. 29-33, (2020).
8. P.K. Fedotov, A.E. Senchenko, K.V. Fedotov, A.E. Burdonov / Hydrometallurgical processing of gold-bearing ore and enrichment products. Moscow, №. 2, 75-84, (2021).
9. ГОСТ 14180-80 Методы отбора и подготовки проб для химического анализа и определения влаги.
10. I.K. Umarova, G.K. Solijonova. Processes of preparing minerals for enrichment / D.T., 176, (2009).